

Abstract: The article discusses the development history, current status and prospects of forensic psychological expertise. Information was also provided about the procedure for conducting a forensic psychological examination and its role in various legal processes. There is also a lot of information about the views and opinions of different people on this issue.

Key words: court, psychology, expertise, trial, investigation, person, attitude, will, emotion, disorder, stress, affect, psychic explosion, legal norm, lawyer, investigator

ФОРМЫ И ПРЕДМЕТ СУДЕБНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ЭКСПЕРТИЗЫ

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается история развития, современное состояние и перспективы судебно-психологической экспертизы. Также была предоставлена информация о порядке проведения судебно-психологической экспертизы и ее роли в различных юридических процессах. Также имеется много информации о взглядах и мнениях разных людей по этому вопросу.

Ключевые слова: суд, психология, экспертиза, суд, следствие, человек, отношение, воля, эмоция, расстройство, стресс, аффект, психический взрыв, правовая норма, адвокат, следователь

It is known that the system of any judicial examination is determined by the system of science, which is its basis, as well as the tasks to be solved in the procedural activity of law enforcement agencies. According to VV Romanov , "the method of forensic psychological examination is the characteristics, circumstances, psychological processes of healthy people participating in criminal and civil cases, the characteristics of their psychological activity, temporary changes of consciousness under the influence of various facts (not suffering from disease), their It is important to determine the objective truth of the evaluation. Therefore, various manifestations of the environment by the participants of the examination system are individual-specific aspects of the psychological reflection, which are important for the correct resolution of criminal and civil cases.

The concepts of general object and general method of forensic psychology are generally homogeneous compared to similar concepts in general psychology. Despite this, in the literature on psychology, a unified opinion about their interpretation has not yet been developed. In such a situation, human psychology (or psychological activity) is considered as a means of psychological research. This agreement is also characteristic of fundamental psychology.

In practical psychology, the general object of psychological research is given a different definition: either human psychology in general, or as psychological activity, in general and unified form. When it comes to the general meaning of psychological exercise, under it are understood individual psychological characteristics, states and processes.

In psychology, "they distinguish different levels of studying a person: in the system of social relations; analysis of personality structure; separate systems of various psychological processes, states, properties. In this study, the formation mechanisms and

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functions of will, emotions, logic of thinking, memory, perception, perception are investigated. In particular, the second and third steps correspond to the psychological research of the exerrt."

Thus, the psychological standard of the individual method of forensic psychological examination is formed by clarifying the general method of psychological research in accordance with the specific task of the examination. However, it is necessary to take into account this legal norm of forensic psychology. What is its content and essence? Any psychological research can not provide proof-of-concept materials, but only in its process there is a research that has identified such important cases. The court determines the legal significance of cases, first of all, based on the existence of an objective connection between the means of proof and the facts. It can be said that forensic-psychological expertise as a legal norm of the formation of a personal system, norms of substantive law are manifested. They contain psychological elements in one form or another, and this is precisely why their legal significance is recognized. It becomes necessary to identify such elements, to correctly describe the controversial legal relationship that caused the court to consider the case during the preliminary judicial investigation.

As noted by MV Kostitsky, psychological expertise is closely related to general psychology and its practical areas, they form the basis of a unique "useful resource" for the development of psychological expertise. In turn, as a specific form of psychological practice, it contributes to the enrichment and improvement of the development of psychological expertise, its "fundamental sciences".

At the same time, the form of psychological expertise can be determined by the needs of practice, but the practical application of psychological knowledge can be a sufficient impetus for the development of the corresponding field of psychological knowledge.

Therefore, the psychology of labor serves as the theoretical base of the psychological labor exerthesis. The research method of labor psychology is the psychological laws of the formation of specific forms of labor activity and the attitude of a person to work, labor activity in production conditions and the conditions of re-training of human labor force.

The method of labor psychological examination is a person's psychological manifestations in the field of labor activity, his ability to a certain form of work, various forms of communication of mistakes and deviations made in the work process.

The method of psychological examination is not to determine the authenticity of the testimony, which is within the authority of the investigator and the court, but to determine the ability to re-imagine and remember information about the facts, which is part of the evidence method, due to the individual characteristics of the psychological processes of the person under investigation.

This description of the method of forensic psychological examination is to a certain extent correct, but it is too narrow, since it covers only the specific purpose of forensic psychological research - the adequate reception and recall by the witness of information relevant to the case. and to determine the ability and characteristics of telling.

As a rule, the tasks of the forensic psychological examination are determined by the competent authorities in each specific situation (investigation and court) and are only broad.

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